

Thesis Title

Study of biodegradation of petroleum contamination Gachsaran lands around fields using a bacterial strain

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Abstract

Oil production and transportation culminates in the release of oil to natural environments with concomitant contamination and toxicity problems. Oil hydrocarbons are harmful for environment, human health and all creatures on our planet. The enhancement of natural biological degradation processes in what is termed bioremediation can be a preferred cost-effective method of removing contaminant hydrocarbons from oil-contaminated environments. The aim of this research is isolation of crude oil degrading bacteria from oil-contaminated soils of Gachsaran's oil fields.

To isolate, the first step was the preparation of a suspension of oil-contaminated soil in distilled water. In the second step a serial dilution was made. Each dilution was cultivated in a medium with agar. Crude oil decomposition and biosurfactant producing testing for all of isolates was carried out via cultivation of these bacteria in peptone water-yeast extract medium with a nitrogen source and 1% crude oil as carbon and energy source.

Three isolates were able to degrade the crude oil. So that the first day there were two phases in the medium, after a few days, these three bacteria degraded the crude oil until there was only one phase left in the medium. Among them one strain was selected as a superior strain by homogenizing until the medium became clear and transparent. Oil displacement area (ODA) was applied for verification of producing biosurfactant.

Physiological and biochemical studies and 16S rDNA analysis reveals this strain is *Bacillus subtilis*. Some optimal growth conditions for the strain were studied using one factor-at-a-time approaches. Growth curve of the strain according to optimal conditions was studied in a 1000-flask and a fermentor (5 litre). Finally the amount of decomposition of pollutant qualitatively was studied.

Keywords: biosurfactant, *Bacillus*, biodegradation, crude oil, Gachsaran